

PREZODE in action
in the global South

Report of the expert workshop:

Community Knowledge and Social Sciences Contributions to Zoonotic Disease Prevention

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Report of the Expert Workshop

Community Knowledge and Social Sciences Contributions to Zoonotic Disease Prevention (project PREZODE – PREACTS - ASAMCO LaoThai, Afd, IRD)

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1. Background: ASAMCO

The PREZODE (PREventing Zoonotic Diseases Emergence) initiative, which the ASAMCO project is tied to, aimed to build resilient socio-ecological systems in order to prevent zoonotic disease emergence while preserving biodiversity and combating poverty, social injustice and food insecurity. The ASAMCO project is the second phase of the PREACTS (PREzode in Action in the global South) project, led by IRD and funded by the French Development Agency (AFD), as the first operational component of the PREZODE initiative.

ASAMCO Laos & Thailand will implement the activities at the border provinces, which will help to prevent zoonotic transboundary diseases, aiming to:

1. Analyze wildlife interfaces: Identify wildlife interaction points and analyze gaps in zoonotic disease prevention, focusing on ecosystems, land use changes, livestock proximity to protected areas, urbanization, and economic activities.
2. Synthesize existing knowledge: Map past and ongoing projects to understand their objectives, methods, outcomes, and geographic focus.
3. Strengthen policies and legislation: Highlight policy and legislative gaps related to wildlife and zoonotic disease management.
4. Develop a comprehensive framework: Create a Theory of Change (ToC) to address zoonotic risks at the ecosystem level with clear targets, strategies, and indicators.
- 5 Foster local innovation: Implement innovative, site-specific actions to prevent, mitigate, and monitor zoonotic diseases in collaboration with local communities and administrations.

To effectively prevent the emergence of infectious diseases with high epidemic potential, a holistic approach in terms of prevention needs to be adopted, using the ‘One Health’ approach (defined by OHHLEP) and the definition of upstream prevention (also defined by OHHLEP).

2. Aims of the workshop

By bringing together experts from multiple disciplines from Humanities and Social Sciences, the workshop aims to highlight how qualitative, community-based approaches can strengthen local knowledge, foster meaningful participation, and ensure that community voices are fully integrated into zoonotic disease prevention. Through these exchanges, the workshop aims to generate shared perspectives and identify concrete pathways for embedding social sciences within interdisciplinary strategies for preventing zoonotic diseases at their source, while outlining actionable recommendations for future ASAMCO–PREZODE activities.

3. Main outputs of the workshop

Despite their increasing recognition within the One Health agenda, the effective integration of social sciences into zoonotic disease prevention remains constrained by several structural, epistemological, and institutional challenges. These obstacles explain why, historically, Humanities and Social Sciences have been underrepresented in disease prevention programmes and why their contributions and mobilizations often arrive late in the research process.

Challenge 1 – *A biomedical dominance and unequal epistemic legitimacy*

Zoonotic disease prevention has long been framed as a technical matter requiring surveillance, diagnostics, and laboratory capacities. As a result:

- Humanities and Social Sciences are often invited only after outbreaks, to “support communication” or “explain behaviours”;
- Ethnographic knowledge is seen as anecdotal or “not evidence-based”- while it produces situated and relational forms of knowledge that follow a different logic of validation than biomedical evidence;
- Geography is often reduced as producing maps - while it can reveal spatial blind spots, scale and administrative boundaries mismatches;
- Local knowledge is marginalized compared to quantitative indicators.

> *This hierarchy of knowledge - not only institutional, but also epistemological- limits Humanities and Social Sciences participation in upstream risk assessment or protocol design.*

Challenge 2 – A tendency to reduce social sciences to behavioral change

In many One Health or public health programs, social sciences are operationalized merely as tools for:

- identifying “non-compliance”;
- improving adherence to biomedical guidelines;
- adjusting risk communication.

> *This behaviorist frame overlooks the complexity of livelihoods, structural inequalities, land tenure issues, and historical relations with the state—elements central to understanding zoonotic risks. Moreover, by training, anthropologists do not aim at modifying the people’s behavior but rather to understand it and highlight its inherent logic. For example, there is an important difference between Anthropology and Applied anthropology and a large misconception of the basics of the discipline.*

Challenge 3 – Institutional fragmentation and lack of Humanities and Social Sciences positions

Most national prevention systems are organized around ministries of health, agriculture, or environment. Humanities and Social Sciences are rarely institutionalized within these structures:

- ministries have no Humanities and Social Sciences units;
- funding mechanisms and grant calls often prioritize surveillance and laboratory screening.

> *This leads to structurally weak integration of Humanities and Social Sciences straight from the initial research framework on disease prevention.*

Challenge 4 – *Limited interdisciplinary literacy*

Collaborations between epidemiologists, ecologists, veterinarians, and Humanities and Social Sciences often stumble upon:

- different definitions of key concepts (risk, exposure, interface);
- incompatible methodological expectations (representativeness vs situatedness);
- divergent temporalities of research (rapid assessments vs long-term fieldwork).

> *Without a shared epistemic space, Humanities and Social Sciences contributions may appear “too slow,” “too qualitative,” or “not operational”.*

Challenge 5 – *Ethical tensions around community engagement*

Anthropologists often witness:

- communities' mistrust toward authorities;
- risks of instrumentalizing local voices for pre-defined agendas;
- difficulty in securing equity and long-term reciprocity.

> *Effective engagement requires ethical sensitivity and time—resources often incompatible with short-term projects.*

Challenge 6 – *Inadequate training pipelines and lack of capacity-building*

There is a scarcity of:

- Humanities and Social Sciences experts trained in One Health concepts;
- students are able to navigate interdisciplinary settings;
- structured programs that integrate Humanities and Social Sciences fieldwork into the project's surveillance systems from the very beginning.

> *Without targeted capacity-building, Humanities and Social Sciences cannot fully contribute to risk assessment or outbreak preparedness.*

Challenge 7 – *Complexity in addressing structural and political determinants* **Zoonotic risk**

This complexity is shaped by:

- land encroachment;
- environmental governance;
- commercial wildlife trade;
- agricultural intensification;
- gendered divisions of labour.

These determinants are politically sensitive. Many institutions prefer technical solutions that do not challenge:

- power relations;
- economic interests;
- state policies.

> *Social Sciences analyses can be perceived as difficult to implement—yet they are necessary to design sustainable prevention.*

3.2. Identification of pathways

Building on the diagnostic presented above, it becomes clear that the absence of Humanities and Social Sciences in zoonotic disease prevention creates blind spots: local priorities remain unheard, culturally meaningful categories of illness are overlooked, and the power relations shaping vulnerabilities are rarely incorporated into risk assessment. To address these gaps, several pathways can be identified where Humanities and Social Sciences offer not only insights but operational contributions.

Pathway 1 – *Translating community knowledge into reliable information*

Ethnography, interviews, and participatory mapping allow researchers to understand how local people understand and categorize animals, seasons, symptoms, or “unusual events.” Such knowledge—often dismissed as “informal”—can be transformed into locally grounded indicators, for example:

- identification of interspecies contact zones, risk gradient (forest-farm-village) and interface typologies (i.e market, slaughterhouse, grazing area...);
- definition of seasonal “risk calendars” mapped onto territories;
- vernacular markers of animal or human illness;
- social or ritual situations increasing proximity between species.

> *This translation requires careful mediation: humanities and social scientists do not simply “extract” information; they can create conceptual bridges between local ontologies and epidemiological frameworks.*

Pathway 2 – *Co-producing preventive tools with communities*

Social sciences can design participatory tools that involve community members in the assessment and reduction of risks:

- community-based early warning systems;
- co-designed research protocols adapted to real-life constraints;
- localized communication strategies built upon vernacular taxonomies.

> *Such co-production avoids the top-down diffusion of biomedical messages that often fail because they ignore cultural logics or livelihood pressures.*

Pathway 3 – *Governing risk through dialogue between sectors*

Institutional analysis helps identify misalignments between veterinary services, public health institutions, forestry departments, and local communities. By documenting how policies are implemented locally and how communities perceive and receive them, Social Sciences reveal governance gaps, conflicts of jurisdiction, and local mistrust toward state interventions. This allows the design of intersectoral platforms where communities become legitimate interlocutors in One Health governance.

Pathway 4 – *Addressing underlying socio-political determinants*

Zoonotic risk is shaped by economic dependency, limited access to services, gender roles, and marginalization of ethnic groups. Recognizing these determinants shifts prevention from behaviour change messaging to structural interventions (veterinary access, land rights, gender-sensitive training programmes).

3.3. Way forward

Axis 1 – *Recruiting and training a pilot batch of interdisciplinary graduated students recognizing the lead from Humanities and Social Sciences in conducting One Health Risk Assessment, with stakeholder and community engagement*

ASAMCO Asia can engage and train young scholars to strengthen interdisciplinary teams. Humanities and Social Sciences should lead the investigation in dialogue with other disciplines (veterinary medicine, public health, environment, conservation ecology). They will document daily practices, mobility, boundaries, and perceptions of disease—dimensions invisible to epidemiology.

Concrete actions:

- Humanities and Social Sciences internship tracks;
- field integration in risk assessment teams;
- modules training in One Health literacy for Humanities and Social Sciences, qualitative methods for other disciplines, in collaboration with SEA OHUN (Southeast Asia One Health University Network).

The group of young graduated students will be recruited from the Experts and be included with one local site of ASAMCO Thailand and Laos (following the geography of intervention).

Axis 2 – *Integrating gender, social differentiation, and marginalized communities*

Patterns of exposure to animal-borne, environmental, and occupational health risks are not evenly distributed. They are shaped by gender, age, social status, and ethnic belonging. These aspects determine who cares for animals, who enters forests and pastures, who handles sick livestock, who participates in training activities, and who holds decision-making roles within communities and administrations.

Effective One Health prevention must therefore explicitly address these social asymmetries by:

- systematically collecting and analysing gender- and age-disaggregated data, while also accounting for ethnic and social positioning;
- ensuring the inclusion of women and youth, but also elders and members from marginalized ethnic communities in workshops, consultations, and co-research activities;
- analysing gendered and socially differentiated divisions of labour;
- recognising and valuing local knowledge systems held by ethnic communities;
- empowering women, youth and members from marginalized groups as key actors in One Health prevention

Axis 3 – Developing a regular webinar for the ASAMCO - PREZODE community

Developing a regular ASAMCO - PREZODE webinar would help consolidate the network of Humanities and Social Sciences researchers involved in zoonotic disease prevention. It would create a stable space for sharing methods, field experiences, and perspectives, while fostering scientific acculturation between Humanities and Social Sciences and other disciplines such as veterinary sciences, conservation ecology, environment, and public health. By encouraging mutual understanding and dialogue, the webinar would strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration across the consortium. Over time, the ideas and discussions emerging from these sessions could lead to a collective editorial project (edited volume) highlighting Humanities and Social Sciences contributions within the One Health agenda.

4. Conclusion

The way forward requires recognizing zoonotic prevention as a social, political, and ecological challenge. Social sciences contribute by revealing logics behind practices, designing participatory tools, strengthening governance, integrating gender and power relations, training new experts, and creating conceptual bridges across disciplines. Prevention then becomes a collaborative, context-sensitive, and ethically grounded process where communities are co-creators of knowledge and action.

5. Definitions and useful links

Applied Anthropology is the use of anthropological theories, methods, and insights to address concrete social, environmental, health, or development issues. It involves close engagement with communities, institutions, and policymakers to co-produce context-specific knowledge and inform practical actions, interventions, or public decision-making.

Epistemic Asymmetry refers to unequal recognition and weighting of different forms of knowledge within decision-making processes, whereby scientific, biomedical, or quantitative knowledge is prioritized over local, experiential, or qualitative knowledge. Such asymmetries influence how risks are assessed, which evidence is considered legitimate, and how prevention strategies are designed, potentially limiting the effectiveness of One Health interventions when locally grounded knowledge is insufficiently integrated.

Ethnoecology is an interdisciplinary field that examines how human societies perceive, understand, and engage with their environments through culturally situated knowledge systems. It focuses on the relationships between humans, other living beings, and ecological processes as shaped by practice, experience, and history. Ethnoecology emphasizes the dynamic and relational character of ecological knowledge rather than fixed classifications. It also attends to issues of power, translation, and recognition between local ecological knowledges and scientific frameworks.

Ethnography is a qualitative research methodology based on long-term, immersive fieldwork that seeks to understand social life from the perspectives of those who live it. Through participant observation, interviews, and everyday engagement, ethnography produces situated knowledge attentive to practices, relationships, power, and meaning in context. Moreover, it is also an analytical approach that emphasizes the situated, relational, and historically embedded nature of knowledge production.

Ethnozoology is the study of relationships between human societies and animals, focusing on how animals are perceived, classified, used, and cared for within specific cultural and ecological contexts. It examines local knowledge, practices, and beliefs concerning animals, including hunting, herding, medicine, symbolism, and interspecies interactions.

Interspecies Interface refers to contexts in which humans, domestic animals, wildlife, and environments interact closely, creating conditions for potential pathogen transmission. These interfaces are not only biological or ecological but are also socially organized and culturally shaped through livelihoods, land use practices, mobility patterns, and governance arrangements.

Local communities, in an anthropological sense, refer to socially and historically constituted collectives often shaped by ethnic identities, shared genealogies, languages, and cultural practices rooted in a specific territory. They are not homogeneous or fixed entities, but internally differentiated groups whose ethnic boundaries are continually negotiated through social relations, power dynamics, and interactions with wider political and economic forces. These communities are

constantly re-made through everyday practices, collective memory, and sustained relations with human and non-human environments.

Local knowledge are plural and situated forms of knowledge produced through lived experience within specific socio-ecological contexts. They are inherently dynamic, continuously recomposed through learning, adaptation, and interaction with changing environments and institutions. Often marginalized within dominant scientific regimes, they raise critical issues of recognition and power. Crucially, they are frequently interspecific, emerging from sustained relations between humans, animals, plants, and landscapes that actively contribute to knowledge production.

Power relations refer to the distribution of authority, resources, and decision-making capacity among actors such as communities, institutions, experts, and governing bodies. They influence whose knowledge is considered legitimate, how priorities are set, and whose interests shape the design and implementation of zoonotic disease prevention and One Health strategies.

Risk perception refers to the ways in which individuals and communities identify, interpret, and prioritize health and environmental risks based on experience, social context, and interactions with institutions. Risk perception shapes everyday practices, responses to prevention measures, and levels of trust in authorities, and may differ from expert or epidemiological assessments while remaining internally coherent and contextually grounded.

Transdisciplinarity refers to an approach to knowledge production that goes beyond disciplinary boundaries by integrating academic disciplines with non-academic forms of knowledge (e.g. local, experiential, professional). It aims to co-produce knowledge through collaboration among researchers and societal actors to address complex, real-world problems in a holistic and context-sensitive way.

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